

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Breeding methods—hybrid

Performance of IR rice hybrids in Ambasamudram, Tamil Nadu, India

P. Shanmugasundaram, K. Mohanasundaram, A. Thangasmy, M. Velusamy, and M. Rangaswamy, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University Rice Research Station (RRS), Ambasamudram 627401, Tamil Nadu, India

We evaluated rice hybrids IR54752A/IR46R, IR54752A/IR54R, and IR54752A/ARC11353R, with IR20 and Co 43 as local checks. Twenty-day-old seedlings were transplanted 26 Jun 1988 and harvested the last week of Oct. Plots were 3 × 1.2 m with a 15- × 10-cm spacing between plants, in a randomized block design, with two replications.

Yields were assessed on whole plots; biometrical observations were taken on 10 plants/replication. Entries also were screened for reaction to major pests and diseases.

Only IR54752A/IR46 yielded higher than the checks, although the differ-

ence from Co 43 was not significant (Table 1). IR54752A/IR46 matured 5 d earlier, had more productive tillers and higher panicle weight than the checks.

All three hybrids were resistant to stem borer, gall fly, brown planthopper, and sheath blight, and moderately resistant to grain discoloration (Table 2). □

Table 2. Reaction of IRR1 rice hybrids to major pests and diseases in the field at RRS, Ambasamudram, Tamil Nadu, India, 1988.

Hybrid or check	Reaction ^a				
	Insects			Diseases	
	Stem borer	Gall fly	Brown planthopper	Sheath blight	Grain discoloration
IR54752A/IR46	1	1	-	3	5
IR54752A/IR54	1	1	-	3	5
IR54752A/ARC11353	1	1	-	3	5
IR20	3	1	5	3	3
Co 43	5	1	3	3	3

^aStandard evaluation system for rice scale.

Table 1. Performance of IRR1 rice hybrids at RRS, Ambasamudram, Tamil Nadu, India, 1988.

Hybrid or check	Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Productive tillers (no.)	Unproductive tillers (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Panicle weight (g)	Yield (t/ha)	Increase over IR20 (%)	Increase over Co 48 (%)
IR54752A/IR46	130	105.2	11.1	1.1	24.5	35.3	5.5	19.5	14.6
IR54752A/IR54	135	95.8	10.1	1.9	26.0	29.3	4.7	2.1	-
IR54752A/ARC11353	135	89.4	9.5	2.5	25.0	32.9	4.7	2.1	-
IR20	133	88.1	8.0	1.5	24.9	28.9	4.6	-	-
Co 43	139	82.3	8.5	2.5	25.0	29.0	4.8	4.3	-
LSD							0.9		
CV (%)							9.4		

Ease of fertility restoration in CMS lines

T. S. Bharaj, G. S. Sidhu, and S. S. Gill, PAU Rice Research Station, P.O. Box 34, Kapurthala, Punjab, India

We evaluated 36 experimental rice hybrids involving cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines V20A, IR46830A, and IR48483A and 12 restorer lines and their male parents during 1987 wet season. Each line was grown in one row of 12 plants at 20- × 20-cm spacing, in a randomized complete block design

with three replications. Check varieties were PR103 (125 d duration) and PR106 (144 d). Data on grain yield and percent spikelet fertility were collected from the center 10 plants of each row.

None of the hybrids outyielded PR106 (see table). Most of them had short duration. When compared with short-duration check PR103, hybrid combinations V20A/PR103 (120 d) and V20A/PAU50-B-25-1-5 (128 d) had significantly higher yields. This indicates that the performance of hybrids should be compared with checks of similar duration.

The CMS lines used have the same (WA) source of cytoplasm imparting male sterility. But they exhibited different fertility restoration with different restorer lines. PAU50-B-25-1-5 was a good restorer for V20A (82.53% fertile spikelets), but a poor restorer for IR46830A and IR48483A (59.93 and 41.82% spikelet fertility, respectively). Responses with other restorer lines were similar. Hybrids with CMS line V20A uniformly exhibited high grain yield and percent filled spikelets, indicating that V20A was the easiest line to restore. □